

Chelating N-ligands and their Transition Metal Complexes. Part I. Ultraviolet Absorption Spectra of *vic*- Oxime Hydrazones

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Substituted hydrazones of the derivatives of 2, 3-dioxobutyric acid 2-oxime have been prepared and their UV absorption spectra in methanol investigated.

vic-Oxime hydrazones having the structural configuration :

are expected to be closely related to *vic*-dioximes for their chelating properties; these properties, however, may be influenced by the substituents present in the hydrazone group. This might be reflected in the UV absorption spectra of these compounds. Hence, in continuation of our studies on N-ligands derived from 1,2-diketones and related substances¹, we have prepared a series of *vic*-oxime hydrazones. The present communication deals with the preparation and UV absorption spectra of the substituted hydrazones of the derivatives of 2,3-dioxobutyric acid 2-oxime (I).

Phenylhydrazones of the derivatives (namely, anilide, *N*-methylanilide, *o*-toluidide, *o*-chloroanilide, and ethyl ester) of 2,3-dioxobutyric acid 2-oxime were prepared from the corresponding derivatives of 2,3-dioxobutyric acid 2-oxime by the action of phenylhydrazine. These compounds are considered to have preferentially the *anti*-configuration (II) similar to the structure suggested for dioximes, obtained from CO-CH₂ compounds².

2, 3-Dioxo-*N*-methylbutyranilide 2-oxime methyl ether was prepared earlier and was found to contain -OMe group and not -NMe group in the methylated oxime group. This and ethyl 2,3-dioxobutyrate 2-oxime methyl ether were converted into the corresponding phenylhydrazones. On analysis, these were found to contain -OMe group as expected.

1. Talati *et al.*, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1964, 27, 159.
2. Ishidata, *Microchim. Acta*, 1938, 3, 203.